

T. V. Vasilieva

Fintech: an overview of the industry and current trends in 2022

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of studying financial technology is determined by the fact that the rapid development of technologies such as blockchain, artificial intelligence, and mobile applications is transforming the financial sector, making it more accessible and efficient.

Fintech is a dynamic field that has a significant impact on the financial sector and the economy as a whole.

The article aims to review the current trends in the financial technology market in 2022.

Materials and Methods. The study materials were articles from peer-reviewed journals. Research methods: case studies of successful and unsuccessful fintech companies to identify factors influencing their success or failure.

Results. Modern technologies allow for the digitization of services and other IT products, so one of the leading trends is global digitalization and the rise of e-commerce and marketplaces. The next trend discussed in the article is the active adoption of big data, machine learning, and artificial intelligence technologies. The fintech market is actively taking advantage of the opportunities created by the COVID-19 crisis. The fintech market pays excellent attention to developing cloud technologies, implementing digital signatures, and developing a fast payment system.

Conclusion. Despite numerous opportunities, the fintech market is facing particular challenges and hurdles. Some of these include a lack of focus on cybersecurity, regulatory complexities, and a lack of customer confidence. Addressing these challenges is integral to the continued development of the fintech market.

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FOR CITATION

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the financial technology study stems from the rapid development of technologies such as blockchain, artificial intelligence, and mobile applications transforming the financial sector, making it more accessible and efficient.

Today's fintech companies offer solutions that meet consumer expectations for convenience, speed, and personalized service. Fintech companies create competition for traditional financial institutions, resulting in better services and lower prices. Fintech enables companies to enter international markets by offering their services in different countries without establishing a physical presence.

Thus, fintech is a dynamically developing area that has a significant impact on the financial sector and the economy as a whole.

The article aims to review the current trends in the financial technology market in 2022.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study materials are based on articles from peer-reviewed journals such as the Journal of Evolutionary Economics, International Journal of Data Science and Analytics, Financial Innovation, Review of Managerial Science, Electronic Commerce Research, and Journal of Financial Services Marketing.

The research material is also based on data obtained from open sources on the Internet, materials from the Big Data Association, and analysis of data from marketing and consulting companies.

Research methods: case studies of successful and unsuccessful fintech companies to identify factors influencing their success or failure.

LITERATURE REVIEW

K. Sood and S. Singh believe that fintech innovations transform the economy and society by democratizing financial services. According to the authors, fintech has received a lot of media attention; however, there is a lack of literature on the impact of financial technology on the overall economic outlook [1].

The authors provide an overview of research on innovative financial enterprises and their challenges, innovative fintech ecosystems, and artificial intelligence techniques for realizing smart fintech [2]. Several other major reviews on financial innovation should also be mentioned: B. Li et al. [3], A. Alaassar et al. [4], etc.

The development of financial technologies varies across countries and regions depending on economic growth, regulation, cultural characteristics, and technology availability.

J. Wang et al. provide an overview of publications related to fintech from 2006 to 2021. According to the authors, China, the USA, the UK, Australia, and South Korea are the most productive countries in the field of fintech [5].

T. Muganyi et al. studied the impact of fintech on the development of China's financial sector in 290 cities and 31 provinces from 2011 to 2018. The authors show that fintech supports financial sector development by improving access (loans), depth (deposits), and savings in financial institutions in China [6].

M. Safiullah and S. R. Paramati studied the impact of fintech companies on the financial soundness of banks. Using a sample of 26 banks from an emerging market (Malaysia) for the period of 2003–2018, the authors found that the development of fintech companies increased the financial soundness of banks over time [7].

N. O. D. Ellili analyzes recent trends in academic literature regarding the relationship between fintech and sustainability. The author's results show that the analysis of the relationship between FinTech and sustainability showed significant growth in 2021, reflecting the importance of financial technology and business innovation [8].

L. A. Joia and R. Proenza write that the financial sector professionals they interviewed in Brazil have little understanding of the potential of fintech and cannot assess the need to develop a legal and regulatory framework for its implementation in emerging markets [9].

According to S. Carby-Valverde et al., despite the emergence of startups in financial services, most companies face significant difficulties in reaching breakeven and survival. The authors analyze a set of Fintech startups that operated in Spain from 2005 to 2017 – most of these firms became unprofitable within three years of their creation [10].

F. Naz et al. explore the opportunities for fintech development during COVID-19 in the MENA region. According to the authors, there are opportunities for employment, decentralization, economic efficiency, networking, and overcoming traditional financial biases [11].

The development of financial technology in the banking sector has become an essential trend in recent years. This is due to several factors, including consumer preferences, technological advances, and regulatory changes.

According to D. Hu et al., the development of financial technology has brought both opportunities and challenges to the risk management of commercial banks. The results obtained

by the authors show that Fintech development significantly reduces risk-taking by commercial banks, and this effect is more pronounced for large banks and banks with a more developed traditional financial base [12].

F. Yin et al. analyzed the impact of the fintech era on the stability of the Chinese banking sector. The authors found that the second wave of fintech helped to reduce non-performing loans and improve financial stability in China [13].

P. L. Tseng and W. C. Guo examine banks' incentives to verify borrowers in a competitive credit market between traditional banks and fintech startups. The authors find that when fintech reduces the cost of screening borrowers applying to banks, banks' incentives to screen are weakened, and vice versa [14].

E. W. Mainardes et al. identify factors affecting customer satisfaction with fintech services. Data were collected from 294 fintech customers using an online questionnaire, and data analysis was performed by structural equation modeling using the partial least squares method. The authors showed that fintech customer satisfaction was influenced by the perceived ease of use through perceived usefulness and perceived risk through trust [15].

T. Roh et al. write that building strong trusting relationships with consumers can be particularly useful for fintech companies that want to create positive attitudes in the minds of consumers and thus motivate them to use services [16].

Thus, the research problem in financial technology encompasses many aspects. Financial technology is evolving, and legislation often fails to keep pace with rapidly changing technologies. The need for new standards and regulatory frameworks creates uncertainty, which hinders innovation and can lead to financial risks. The complexity of interactions between traditional banking systems and new fintech solutions requires in-depth research. Integration challenges may hinder the effective adoption of new technologies. More research is needed on how consumers perceive and use financial technology. Psychological, behavioral, and educational barriers significantly influence technology adoption. Financial technology is often closely linked to the volatility of financial markets. Understanding the factors affecting the market and investors' behavior is essential to ensure the sustainability of fintech.

RESULTS

Financial technology, as a result of the development of information technologies in the electronic economy, affects all spheres of life and activities of modern people. The fintech industry is developing so rapidly that it can be said that it and banks, in general, are driving technological progress in Russia and the world.

The main trends in the fintech market are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Main trends in the fintech market in 2022

(URL: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/top-5-trends-fintech-2022-cwut-kashish-pahwa>)

1. Global digitalization, the rise of e-commerce and marketplaces. The world is digitizing. Bill Gates once said that in the future “there will be two types of businesses... those that are on the Internet, and those that are out of business”. Modern technologies make it possible to digitize services and other IT products. Almost any product (service) can be obtained from the comfort of one's home using mobile technologies. According to forecasts, by 2025, the entire digital payments market is expected to reach 11.95 trillion dollars. Worldwide, the number of people using digital payments can grow by 6% to 4.43 billion people in 2023, and by 2025, the number of digital payment users will reach almost five billion people [17].

The flourishing of marketplaces gradually leads to the loss of search engine audiences. Having decided to purchase, an Internet user goes not to search engines but directly to marketplaces. Thus, search engines' usual business model becomes irrelevant. Search engines do not receive as much revenue from simple information requests as they do from requests to purchase a product or service.

2. Active implementation of big data, machine learning, and artificial intelligence technologies. This trend is widespread in industry and agriculture, but in the banking sector, up to 70% of analytics tasks are solved using artificial intelligence technologies. In 2022, the Russian market was transformed, and new opportunities for developing the big data industry emerged. The dynamics of the global big data market are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Dynamics of the global big data market, billion dollars.

Big data and artificial intelligence technologies in the banking sector are used in most processes, including voice assistants, call center work, chatbots, and decision-making on loan issuance. In particular, machine learning and artificial intelligence are increasingly used to automate financial processes and make better management decisions [18].

The Big Data Association (BDA), registered on October 12, 2018, in 2019 developed a document entitled “Big Data Strategy to 2024” [19], according to which the contribution of big data technologies to GDP by 2024 could be between 0.3% and 1.8%. According to the Big Data Development Strategy, the consolidated actions of the government and business can ensure the growth of the big data market by 90% to 319 billion rubles by the end of 2024.

3. Implications of COVID-19. The fintech market is actively taking advantage of the opportunities created by the COVID-19 crisis. Social distancing has led to the active use of digital wallets, which are growing rapidly, and countries are engaged in a virtual battle to set national standards. Since the onset of the pandemic, the use of digital wallets has grown to 83%, and it is predicted that the industry will exceed \$10 trillion per year by 2025. Moreover, more than 779 billion digital transactions were made worldwide in 2020, which is expected to make cash payments the least common payment method [20].

4. The rise of cloud technologies. Cloud technology in the financial market combines a cloud-based automated workplace, API technologies and their implementing components, a development environment, generic servers, and necessary hardware. Using the cloud, companies do not need to maintain a local chat server and local deployment of software solutions, as these services are placed in the cloud, allowing fast access to data. In this context, the experience of banks operating exclusively in the virtual space is fascinating. Such banks are

called “neobanks, digital banks”. Such banks have no physical (offline) offices, exist only in the cloud, and communicate with their customers using mobile applications. Digital banks derive their revenues from transactions and premium account subscriptions.

5. Digital signatures. Digital signatures play an essential role in the financial technology industry. They are electronic codes used to validate and sign various financial documents and transactions. Due to their reliability and security, digital signatures are becoming increasingly popular in the fintech market. One of the main advantages of digital signatures is the ability to ensure the identification and authenticity of the identity of participants in financial transactions. Digital signatures verify the authenticity and authorship of electronic documents such as contracts, agreements, financial statements, and other essential documents. As a result, digital signatures help prevent fraud and document forgery, which is critical in the financial technology industry. Another crucial aspect of digital signatures in the fintech market is their simplicity and ease of use. Electronic signatures allow users to complete financial transactions and sign documents online without the need for physical presence or paper documentation. This makes the process faster, more efficient, and more convenient for everyone involved.

Overall, digital signatures, as a modern financial tool, play a key role in the fintech market, providing security, efficiency, and convenience in various financial transactions and processes. Their use contributes to the development of technological solutions, improves customer experience, and reduces bureaucratic processes. Digital signatures will likely become even more sought after and widely used in the fintech market, bringing new opportunities and innovations to this dynamic and rapidly evolving industry.

6. Fast payment system. The fast payment system is unique. In many countries, anyone can send a payment to another person free of charge using the fast payment system. This leads to cheaper payments [21].

7. Digital financial assets and the digital ruble. Digital financial assets are one of the main components of the modern economy. In light of recent technological advances and the development of blockchain technology, the concept of financial assets has undergone significant changes. Instead of traditional currencies such as dollars or euros, digital monetary units can be used as digital tokens or coins. The digital ruble is one example of such a digital asset [22].

8. Remote identification and a unified biometric system. The need for physical identification is gradually disappearing. It is possible to open deposits and bank accounts remotely using biometric technologies. Biometric systems identify people through unique physical characteristics such as voice, face, fingerprints, and iris. In its beginnings, biometrics was mainly used in forensics. One of the early pioneers in biometric identification was

the French criminalist Alphonse Bertillon, who created the “bertillonage” method. This technique involved identifying criminals by their unique physical features.

In the commercial sphere, the development of biometrics received a significant boost in 2013 with the launch of the iPhone with fingerprint recognition technology, known as Touch ID. Biometric identification became the basis for launching payment services such as Apple Pay, Samsung Pay, and Android Pay. This was a significant breakthrough in the application of biometrics. In 2018, Mastercard introduced an innovative biometric card. This card combines chip and fingerprint recognition technologies, allowing users to purchase using their unique biometric identifier. It was essential in developing biometric technology, providing convenience and security in modern financial transactions.

DISCUSSION

Financial technology holds significant promise due to several key factors:

Increased digitalization. With the increased use of mobile devices and the internet, more people and businesses are turning to digital financial services. This creates demand for innovative solutions that can improve access to finance and simplify financial transactions.

Technology innovation. Technologies such as blockchain [23], artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data continue to evolve and offer new opportunities to create more efficient and secure financial services.

Financial inclusion. Fintech can play an essential role in providing access to financial services to people who have not traditionally had access to them [24], including small and medium-sized enterprises and people living in remote and rural areas.

Changing consumer habits. Consumers are becoming more demanding of financial services, expecting convenience, speed, and personalization. Fintech companies that can meet these expectations have a good chance of success.

Regulatory changes. Many countries are beginning to adapt their regulatory frameworks to support innovation in fintech, which can help drive growth in the sector. However, this also creates compliance challenges.

Competition with traditional financial institutions [25]. Fintech companies are becoming serious competitors to conventional banks and financial institutions, which can lead to better services and lower prices for consumers.

Globalization. Fintech has the potential to spread globally, allowing companies to enter new markets and offer their services in different countries.

Sustainability. There has been a growing interest in sustainable and socially responsible investments [26]. Fintech can contribute to the development of green finance and sustainable business models.

Thus, fintech is a dynamic field with many opportunities for innovation and growth, which makes it attractive to researchers, entrepreneurs, and investors.

CONCLUSION

The fintech market in Russia is experiencing significant development. This sector is attracting attention from local startups and large international companies, showing its potential and prospects. One of the main reasons for the growing popularity of fintech in Russia is the increasing number of Internet users and the development of online banking. Many financial institutions are starting to provide services to clients through online platforms, which increases their convenience and accessibility. In addition, e-wallets and payment systems are becoming increasingly popular due to their ease of use and high degree of security. However, despite the numerous opportunities, the fintech market in Russia faces specific challenges and barriers. These include a lack of attention to cybersecurity, regulatory complexities, and insufficient customer trust. Addressing these challenges is essential for the further development of the fintech market in Russia. Overall, the Russian fintech market is showing growth and development and offers many opportunities for innovation in the financial sector.

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INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Tatiana V. Vasilieva (Russia, St. Petersburg) – Associate Professor, Cand. Sci. (Econ.). North-West Institute of Management – branch. The Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration. E-mail: 18021811@mail.ru

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